

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

OBSTACLES TO EFFECTIVE STEM EDUCATION IN GEORGIAN UNIVERSITIES"

Davit Sarishvili,

PhD, student,

Grigol Robakidze University, Tbilisi, Georgia,

Davit Sikharulidze

Associate Professor,

East European University, Tbilisi, Georgia

Abstract

This paper explores the challenges of implementing STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) education in higher education institutions in Georgia. The study employs a quantitative research method, surveying academic staff and undergraduate students to identify key issues hindering the effective development of STEM programs. The findings reveal several significant challenges, including insufficient funding for STEM programs and infrastructure, limited access to advanced technologies and laboratory facilities, a shortage of qualified STEM instructors, and difficulties in integrating interdisciplinary STEM concepts into curricula. The results also indicate that while gender inequality is perceived as a relatively less critical issue, there is still a need for further efforts to overcome gender stereotypes and encourage girls and women to fully engage in STEM education and careers. Additionally, the study highlights varying levels of interest among students towards different STEM fields, with computer science, mathematics, biology, and medical sciences being the most popular. The paper concludes by emphasizing the necessity of comprehensive institutional efforts, including adequate financial support, infrastructure improvement, faculty development, curriculum modernization, and the strengthening of interdisciplinary and practical components to enhance the quality and competitiveness of STEM education in Georgian universities.

Keywords: STEM, Higher education, Challenges, Gender in STEM, Students

1. Introduction

The forthcoming fourth industrial revolution will demand fresh standards and qualifications from personnel, necessitating their retraining [20]. Consequently, there is a current global emphasis on STEM education, evident in both Georgia and worldwide. STEM, an acronym encompassing scientific and technical fields in education and manufacturing, embodies didactic features that endorse interdisciplinary, practice-oriented approaches to natural sciences and mathematics [16].

While contemporary scientific discourse presents various models of STEM education, scholars concur that it represents an innovative educational paradigm facilitating the acquisition and integration of knowledge pertaining to scientific, technological, engineering, and mathematical domains. Its primary objective is to equip graduates with the requisite skills for professional endeavors, particularly problem-solving and task performance through the cultivation of scientific thinking and STEM competencies [1].

However, the implementation of STEM education encounters numerous challenges, a matter underscored in multiple studies [10], including those conducted in Georgia. Notably, one such challenge pertains to fostering interest in STEM careers. Despite concerted efforts, gender disparity remains pronounced within the

STEM sector, particularly at advanced career stages [2], [17]. In Europe, gender parity remains elusive, with horizontal segregation persisting in STEM higher education. A parallel situation exists in Georgia, where the feminization of fields such as education and humanities is evident, with female enrollment dominating at 84.3% and 76.1%, respectively. Conversely, male predominance is observed in technical and scientific disciplines like computer science (81.1%) and engineering (83.2%), reflecting the perception of these fields as traditionally "masculine" and thus deterring women from pursuing them. Similarly, fields like life sciences and health-social security exhibit higher female representation (66.8% and 57.9%, respectively), albeit with a less pronounced gender gap compared to humanities and technical fields. The enrollment distribution in mathematics and statistics, as well as architecture-construction programs, demonstrates relative gender balance, albeit slightly favoring male students (49.7% and 55.4%, respectively) [14]. These trends underscore the enduring dichotomy between "feminine" and "masculine" spheres within higher education, a phenomenon attributed to social stereotypes, familial and societal influences on career choice, insufficient encouragement for women in technical and natural science domains, among other factors.

Figure 1.

Admission of students to higher educational institutions by programs and gender 2023 -2024 academic year

Educational Programs	Man	Woman
Education	84,3	15,7
humanitarian sciences	76,1	23,9
Sciences about life	66,8	33,2
physical sciences	31,6	68,4
Mathematics and statistics	50,3	49,7
Computer case	18,9	81,1
Engineering and engineering work	16,8	83,2
Manufacturing and processing industries	27,0	73,0
Architecture and construction	44,6	55,4
Agriculture	28,0	72,0
Health care and social security	57,9	42,1

Thus, gender inequality persists within STEM education [9], stemming from various factors. Female students encounter numerous obstacles in STEM education, including inadequate family support, stereotypes, and deficient infrastructure, which pose significant impediments to achieving educational equity [9]. This issue is particularly pronounced in the field of engineering [4], [6], [11], [13], [18].

One contributing factor to the disinterest in STEM careers may be the subpar quality of foundational STEM education, compounded by the absence of STEM labs, student startups, and other facilities necessary for engineering students to cultivate their STEM skills. Some researchers posit that students' inclination towards STEM careers is largely contingent upon project-based learning [8]. STEM education can be delineated as a comprehensive approach enabling students to translate knowledge and skills acquired in science and mathematics into engineering products with technological assistance [10]. Moreover, STEM educational initiatives incorporate practical tasks aimed at harmonizing theoretical and practical aspects, with a focus on the pragmatic facets of academic disciplines [15].

When assessing the compatibility of the novel STEM approach with the traditional one, it is essential to recognize that the challenge lies not only in revamping the educational system but also in ensuring the conceptual and institutional frameworks are primed for such a transition, notably through the development of new paradigms. Additionally, the content of STEM teacher training often neglects interdisciplinary collaboration and the integration of requisite technology for project-based and phenomenon-based learning. These deficiencies can engender a waning interest in STEM education and a dearth of skilled professionals in various industries, exacerbating workforce shortages. The scarcity of scientific and technical personnel further imperils the national competitiveness of the country. Against this backdrop, the study aims to investigate the hurdles associated with implementing STEM education in Georgian universities.

2. Methodology

2.1 Population and sample group

The study employed a quantitative research methodology, targeting both academic staff and undergraduate students within the university setting. The sample comprised 216 academic staff (129 women and 87 men) and 226 undergraduate students (130 women and 96 men) from various universities in Georgia. While the mean age of the students was 21, their ages ranged from 18 to 25 years. An empirical assessment of the questionnaire's reliability and validity was conducted using a convenience sample. The questionnaire, developed by the researcher based on a literature review, incorporated items drawn from previous instruments created by other scholars [7], [19].

2.2 Data analysis

During the questionnaire development phase, the content validity of each item was assessed using the item index - object congruence method, with an acceptable threshold set at a coefficient of 0.6-1. To assess the questionnaire's reliability, a pilot study involving 30 academic staff and 30 students, distinct from the selected sample group, was conducted. Data obtained from the pilot study were analyzed using Cronbach's alpha coefficient via statistical software, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.91.

In terms of data analysis pertaining to the challenges associated with implementing STEM education at the university level, preliminary analysis involved computing basic statistical measures such as frequency distribution, percentages, arithmetic mean, and standard deviation. Data were collected using a five-point rating scale, ranging from 1 (indicating less interest or strong disagreement) to 5 (indicating high interest or strong agreement).

3. Results of Challenges of STEM Approach in Higher Education of Georgia

The data for this study were gathered via a questionnaire focused on the Challenges of Implementing STEM Approaches in Higher Education. Figure 1 presents the results of a one-sample t-test reflecting respondents' perspectives on the various obstacles linked with the adoption of STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics) approaches in universities. The analysis unveils several noteworthy findings.

Figure 2.

The views of academic staff on the challenges of STEM education in higher education

	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
Lack of student interest in STEM fields.	53,061	305	0,000	3,003
Insufficient funding for STEM programs and resources, particularly infrastructure.	66,892	305	0,000	3,520
Limited access to advanced technologies and laboratory facilities.	58,244	305	0,000	3,310
Shortage of qualified STEM instructors and academic staff.	56,385	305	0,000	3,278
Gender disparity in enrollment in STEM majors.	47,692	305	0,000	2,422
Difficulty integrating interdisciplinary STEM concepts into the curriculum.	61,036	305	0,000	3,092
High dropout rates among students in STEM programs.	58,710	305	0,000	2,853
Absence of integrated, creative, practical, real-world issues in the curriculum (educational programs), and a dearth of experimental, active teaching approaches.	59,498	305	0,000	3,163
Scarcity of employment prospects for STEM graduates.	53,376	305	0,000	3,157

For all the enumerated challenges, the values of the t statistic are considerably high (ranging from 47.692 to 66.892), with the corresponding p values (Sig. 2-tailed) registering as zero. This suggests that the null hypothesis positing a population mean of zero for each challenge is rejected at the 0.05 significance level. Consequently, the evaluations provided by the respondents significantly deviate from zero. The Mean Difference metrics span from 2.422 to 3.520, indicating a general consensus among respondents regarding the existence of these challenges. However, the extent of concurrence varies across different issues.

The highest mean score (3.520) is attributed to "Insufficient funding of STEM programs and resources (infrastructure)," underscoring respondents' perception of this challenge as paramount for the advancement of STEM education. Subsequent challenges receive relatively high average ratings, namely: "Limited access to advanced technologies and laboratory facilities" (3.310), "Shortage of qualified STEM instructors and academic staff" (3.278), "Lack of curriculum-integrated, creative, practical, real-world issues, experiential active learning approach" (3.163),

and "lack of employment prospects for STEM graduates" (3.157). Respondents identify these factors as substantial barriers hindering the effective execution of STEM programs.

Relatively lower, yet still notable, mean scores are assigned to items such as "students' lack of interest in STEM fields" (3.003), "difficulty integrating interdisciplinary STEM concepts into the curriculum" (3.092), and "high student dropout rates from STEM programs" (2.853). This suggests potential challenges in maintaining student motivation and engagement in the learning process.

The lowest average score (2.422) pertains to "gender disparity in enrollment in STEM courses." Although this indicator remains statistically distinct from zero, respondents appear to perceive it as less urgent compared to the other listed challenges.

Figure 2 displays the outcomes of a one-sample t-test delineating the perspectives of university undergraduate students concerning gender issues within the STEM field. The analysis unveils several significant trends.

Figure 3.

University students' views regarding gender in STEM

	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
In the IT field, males are more effective than females	-13,911	1227,823	0,000	-0,977
There are more men than women in STEM studies because they are more motivated.	-11,099	1155,788	0,000	-0,752
Girls are not as interested in STEM subjects as boys	-12,289	1175,827	0,000	-0,874
Girls have less natural aptitude than boys for STEM subjects.	-10,749	1215,128	0,000	-0,747
In TEM employment fields, males have higher professional growth opportunities than females]	-7,817	1163,778	0,000	-0,560
University studies in STEM are generally more attractive to boys.	-11,066	1151,842	0,000	-0,763

The t-statistic values for all examined provisions are negative, ranging from -7.817 to -13.911. Nonetheless, the corresponding p-values (Sig. 2-tailed) are uniformly 0.000, indicating statistical significance at the 0.05 level and suggesting that the disparity between the

mean estimates and the null test value (0) is not random but reflects systematic trends. Negative t-values and mean differences (Mean Difference) suggest that respondents, on average, either disagree or lean towards

disagreement with all statements pertaining to gender stereotypes and inequality in the STEM field.

The most pronounced negative attitude is evident towards the statement: "In the field of IT, the male gender is more effective than the female gender" ($t = -13.911$, Mean Difference = -0.977). This outcome signifies a strong rejection of this stereotype by the majority of respondents. Similarly high negative values are observed for the following assertions: "Girls are not as interested in STEM subjects as boys" ($t = -12.289$, Mean Difference = -0.874), "There are more men than women in STEM studies because they are more eager" ($t = -11.099$, Mean Difference = -0.752), and "University studies in STEM are generally more attractive to boys" ($t = -11.066$, Mean Difference = -0.763). These results indicate widespread rejection of stereotypical

beliefs regarding girls' interests and motivations in STEM.

Relatively lower but still statistically significant negative evaluations are observed for the statements: "Girls have less natural abilities for STEM issues than boys" ($t = -10.749$, Mean Difference = -0.747) and "Men in STEM employment fields have higher professional growth opportunities than women" ($t = -7.817$, Mean Difference = -0.560). These findings suggest that despite an overall negative trend, some respondents are still influenced by traditional gender stereotypes.

The figure 3 depicts data concerning interest levels in various subject areas and their corresponding employment opportunities. Respondents were requested to rate each area on a 5-point scale, where 1 indicates least interest and 5 signifies high interest. Upon conducting data analysis, several key trends emerge:

Figure 4.

Interest in STEM careers

	1	2	3	4	5
Physics: Aviation Engineer, Alternative Energy Technician, Laboratory Technician, Physicist, Astronomer.	18,0	17,1	30,8	17,8	16,3
Biology and Zoology: Biological Technician, Biological Scientist, Plant Breeder, Crop Laboratory Technician, Animal Scientist, Geneticist, Zoologist.	16,9	14,6	31,9	18,3	18,3
Mathematics: Accountant, Applied Mathematician, Economist, Financial Analyst, Mathematician, Statistician, Market Researcher, Stock Market Analyst.	15,3	11,9	28,2	19,0	25,6
Earth Science: Geologist, Weather Forecaster, Archaeologist, Geologist.	17,4	14,2	32,8	17,8	17,8
Computer Science: Computer Support Specialist, Computer Programmer, Computer and Network Technician, Game Designer, Computer Software Engineer, Information Technology Specialist.	11,2	10,7	29,2	19,1	29,8
Medical science: clinical laboratory technologist, medical scientist, biomedical engineer, epidemiologist, pharmacologist.	18,7	16,0	31,3	16,9	17,1
Chemistry: chemical technician, chemist, chemical engineer.	22,2	16,4	31,7	14,7	15,0
Energy: Electrician, electrical engineer, HVAC technician, nuclear engineer, systems engineer, alternative energy systems installer or technician.	21,6	17,1	31,7	16,1	13,6
Engineering: Civil, Industrial, Agricultural or Mechanical Engineers, Welder, Auto Mechanic, Engineering Technician, Construction Manager.	22,6	16,8	31,0	15,1	14,6
Entrepreneur or Business Scientist: Designing STEM-Related Products Through Innovation.	17,8	13,2	31,7	19,8	17,6
Science teachers/pedagogues: Educators who teach STEM and its applications in schools and universities	22,8	13,6	32,7	15,0	16,0

The highest interest is evident in computer science and related career opportunities. 29.8% of respondents rate their interest as "5", indicating high interest, while 19.1% choose a rating of "4". This underscores the popularity of the computer field and the increasing demand for relevant qualifications. Mathematics and related career options also garner significant interest, with 25.6% indicating maximum interest and 19% expressing high interest. The significance of this field is underscored by its foundational role in numerous STEM disciplines.

Biology, zoology, and medical sciences attract considerable interest among respondents, with approximately 34-36% expressing interest in these areas, rating them as "5" or "4". This reflects the relevance of these fields and young people's readiness to pursue careers in the health sector.

Physics, earth sciences, chemistry, energy, and engineering evoke interest among a relatively smaller

number of respondents. Approximately 29-34% of respondents rate these areas as "5" or "4". This can be attributed to the perceived complexity of these disciplines and the lack of societal awareness regarding relevant professions.

Entrepreneurship/business sciences and science teaching/pedagogy are of interest to 37.4% and 31% of respondents, respectively, who rate them as "5" or "4". This underscores the continued prioritization of developing entrepreneurial skills and promoting STEM education.

Conclusion

The analysis underscores the necessity of a comprehensive institutional endeavor for the advancement of STEM education, encompassing adequate financial backing, infrastructural enhancements, recruitment and retention of highly skilled personnel, curriculum modernization, reinforcement of interdisciplinary and practical

components, as well as the enhancement of student motivation and career prospects. While gender inequality was perceived as a relatively less pressing issue by respondents, some strides in this realm may already be discernible. Nonetheless, comprehensive reforms are imperative to enable universities to offer globally competitive STEM education aligned with labor market demands.

Moreover, the findings reveal a significant critical stance among the majority of respondents towards gender stereotypes in the STEM domain. Nevertheless, the presence of individual variations and dissenting opinions underscores ongoing disparities in societal perceptions regarding women's roles and opportunities in STEM. Addressing these issues necessitates concerted efforts to raise awareness, challenge gender biases, and empower girls and women to actively participate in STEM education and careers. Developing pertinent policies and implementing measures to ensure gender equality in STEM is paramount.

Furthermore, the data highlights varying levels of interest among STEM fields, with computer sciences, mathematics, biology-zoology, and medical sciences eliciting the highest interest, while physics, chemistry, energy, and engineering garner relatively less enthusiasm. This discrepancy may stem from factors such as varying levels of awareness among youth, perceptions of these fields as challenging, or a lack of perceived attractiveness.

To foster STEM careers and cultivate sought-after skills among young people, concerted efforts are needed both within the education system and through targeted projects in the civil sector. This concerted approach will facilitate the training of qualified personnel in these domains, aligning them with labor market requirements. Additionally, strengthening the career guidance system is crucial to provide young individuals with comprehensive information about STEM career opportunities, enabling them to make informed choices.

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